

LINGUOCULTUROLOGICAL AND SEMANTIC FEATURES OF POETIC TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6985288>

Abstract. Getting to know terms of translation is essential part of the communication of the job. Merely, finding an appropriate translation of the term and employing it in the proper circumstances are fundamental questions in using the terms among the languages. The main purpose of the article is to tackle the issues of translating poetic terms from English into Uzbek. As poetic terms are the leading elements of literary texts and some terms of poetry are diversified from various sources like literary dictionaries.

Keywords: allusion, talmeh, mythology.

ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ И СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПОЭТИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ

Аннотация. Знакомство с терминами перевода является важной частью общения на работе. Просто поиск подходящего перевода термина и его использование в надлежащих обстоятельствах являются фундаментальными вопросами использования терминов между языками. Основной целью статьи является решение вопросов перевода поэтических терминов с английского на узбекский язык. Поскольку поэтические термины являются ведущими элементами литературных текстов, а некоторые термины поэзии диверсифицированы из различных источников, таких как литературные словари.

Ключевые слова: аллюзия, талмех, мифология.

INTRODUCTION

Poetry, as one of the literature subjects has many differences from the others. Learning poetry is not easy as learning fiction, drama or the others because the material of this subject is poem-words that consist of figurative language and sometimes connotation and it is difficult to interpret. However, the language of poems is not only amusement and decoration, it aids to the poet's messages to the readers, also entails in social fact, human mature, and personal experiences. Kennedy, states that many readers who have no trouble understanding and enjoying prose find poetry difficult. The difficulty of poetry is sometimes it can't be understood and enjoyed on first reading, because a poem has to be read slowly, carefully, attentively and more than one reading.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In particular poetic terms may differ depending on the language or may not find the equivalent. English poetic terms refer to the uniqueness of English lyrical art. However, when translating into Uzbek, of course, it is necessary to analyze the similarities and differences between Uzbek poetic arts and poetic terms with English poetry. It is analyzed in the example of allusion.

“An allusion may be defined as the mention of the name of a real person, historical event or literary character which is not simply a straightforward reference (as in “Hercules was an ancient Greek hero”) but which conjures up some extra meaning embodying some quality or characteristic for which word has come to stand. So, we can describe a miser as a Scrooge, a

strong man as a Hercules, a beautiful woman as a Venus.” Allusion in English Literature As it can be detected that allusion is a kind of stylistic device which can make the work, play, poem or even the speech more expressive and informative by giving a hint to some kind of wider and eligible person or an object or even a historical event.

An allusion in a poem refers to a person, place, historical event, or ancient source such as the Bible, mythology, ancient poets etc. It refers outside of the poem itself to evoke a mental picture, create an image, and set the poem in a larger context or setting "All Overgrown by Cunning Moss" By Emily Dickinson All overgrown by cunning moss, All interspersed with weed, The little cage of "Curren Bell" In quiet "Haworth" laid. In this poem, famed American poet Emily Dickinson makes an allusion to Curren Bell, which was the pen name for English author Charlotte Bronte, who is most famous for her novel Jane Eyre. Dickinson also alludes to the English village of Haworth, where Bronte died.

RESULTS

The problem with using allusion in poems is that it can lead to creating a poem that will not be universally understood. If you make your reference obscure, it means that the people who do understand them will love them, but the people who can't understand them feel alienated. Maya Angelou's poem, "The Detached," includes an allusion to Bluebeard. We die, Welcoming Bluebeards to Our Darkening closets, Stranglers to our outstretched Necks, Stranglers, who neither care no Care to know that death internal. Without a basic understanding of Bluebeard, "The Detached" loses its full meaning. Who or what is a Bluebeard? A quick trip to Wikipedia tells us that Bluebeard is a French folktale. "The tale tells the story of a wealthy violent man in the habit of murdering his wives and attempts of one wife to avoid the fate of her predecessors."

Allusion in Uzbek Literature. Using allusion in poetry comes with some risk. Some readers will not pause to look up allusions they are not already familiar with. In fact, some may not recognize an allusion at all. Allusions to famous works of literature are also common, but again, they are dependent on the reader's familiarity with the referenced material. It can be observed in some languages, although it is used with another name in other languages. For instance: in Uzbek literature there is no any kind of device which is named like "Allusion", however it has the device "Talmeh" which carries out the same function as Allusion in Uzbek literature. "Talmeh" ("to look at, glance at") is the art of making a reference to famous historical events, myths, literary works or proverbs in poems or plays. Poets reference to "Farhad and Shirin", "Layli and Majnun", "Tokhir and Zukhra" which are known in the East as symbols of "Love". When the reader sees the reference to this or that name, the event or the person or the love between them, their fight to reach their love, their tragedy can come to his or her mind and he or she can imagine and analyze them deeply. For example:

Lutfi's Husnin aslidin seningdek oy paydo bo'lmadi. Mohi Ka'noniydag'i ham muncha zebo bo'lmadi.

DISCUSSION

When the reader sees the phrase "Mohi Ka'noniy", he or she can immediately imagine one of the famous epic "Yusuf and Zulaykho". Yusuf's image can be detected. It is known that Yusuf is the person who has nine beauties of the all ten beauties of the world. The reader can compare the two lovers, if one of them is so beautiful, how beautiful the second can be and she can be more beautiful than Yusuf. In Uzbek poetry in the East, it is common making a reference

to famous lovenarrations and their characters. Alisher Navoi's

Sendin o'rgangan kibi Laylou Shirin zulmu kin,
Mendin o'rganmak kerak Majnun bila Farhod ishq,
Uvaysiy's Jafo tegdi boshimg'a Layliyu, Shirinu Uzrodin,
Bukun Vomiq ila Majnunu Farhodimni sog'indim.

They are the examples of the art of "Talmeh" in Uzbek literature. Uzbek language is highly rich inexpressive vocabulary and stylistic devices like allusion.

CONCLUSIONS

To put it in a nutshell, I pen down saying that above-mentioned ways has shed light on the translation of poetic terms as a problem that causes real translation challenges. It attempted to focus on the translation of the terms in general. Furthermore, conducting ideas in the above-proposed areas of the issue would contribute to overcome a major translation problem, that is the translation of poetry, and it means it does need to be investigated again particularly by any researchers who has willing of contributing to the development of English-Uzbek poetic translation in general.

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